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Sahel Collaboration and
Communication (SCC)

RAPID LEARNING NOTE

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DATA RESPONSIBILITY AMONG DIGITAL WORKING GROUP MEMBERS IN NIGER AND BURKINA FASO

Information exchange is the foundation of collaborating, learning and adapting to achieve resilience outcomes. The responsibility of those collecting, using and sharing resilience information is to first ‘do no harm’ by making data security and privacy protection a priority. Data responsibility is not just a compliance issue – although USAID Administrative Directives require specific information system capabilities and high security standards. Confidence that information is safe to share as an evidence base for making and communicating decisions promotes timely and appropriate resilience action for collective impact. Accordingly, the Digital Working Group (DWG) hosted data responsibility sessions in May 2022 in Niger and Burkina Faso which aimed to discuss the key concepts and tools of data responsibility and identify actions to be taken to safeguard personal data.

This learning note sets out the key considerations and recommendations from these constructive reflections about how USAID activities in Niger and Burkina Faso should safely collect, use, store, and share information.

DIGITAL WORKING GROUP (DWG):

The DWG aims to provide a framework for collaboration and coordination on digital initiatives for USAID activities in Niger and Burkina Faso while implementing USAID's digital strategy, which emphasizes the responsible use of digital technologies and strengthening digital ecosystems. It addresses the high risk of duplication of investment in digital tools and uncoordinated or poorly designed approaches to digital development. The DWG includes USAID activity focal points and national agencies (ANPTIC – *Agence Nationale de Promotion des TIC*¹ in Burkina Faso and ANSI – *Agence Nationale pour la Société de l'Information* in Niger).

This product is aimed at resilience programs and USAID implementing partners working on collaborative activities to collectively achieve USAID's strategic development objectives under the RISE II, BRIDGE and Governance, Peace, and Social Cohesion initiatives in Niger and Burkina Faso.

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KEY CONSIDERATIONS

For USAID-funded activities, it is important projects internalize USAID's requirements for the use of digital data, especially in a context such as the Sahel, which is plagued by various security challenges.

KEY USAID GUIDANCE AND REQUIREMENTS CAN BE SUMMARIZED AS:

- Plan for data use and clarifying how data will be managed from collection, transmission, storage, analysis, and documentation.
- Ensure that information is used responsibly in organizations is everyone's business regardless of position. There is a tendency to think that only IT security staff, privacy experts or even data managers are concerned, but that is not the case.
- Help everyone understand data classification (understanding what is personal, sensitive, non-personal and public data).
- Identify which data can or cannot be released publicly due to privacy concerns.
- Handle sensitive data appropriately by considering options that can limit data collection, ensure encryption, improve tracking of Personally Identifiable Information (PII) and strengthen staff training.
- Use or adapt widely-used tools for data privacy: [Data Privacy Checklist](#) and [Privacy Impact Assessment](#)

MINIMUM DATA RESPONSIBILITY STANDARDS

- Protect privacy
- Respect agency
- Informed consent
- Allow correction
- Redress for harm
- Improve interventions and adapt
- Promote social equity

EFFECTIVE MEASURES FOR DATA PRIVACY

- Remove identifiable information
- Track Privacy Impact Assessment
- Monitor privacy throughout the lifecycle of the data
- Identify privacy risks throughout the information management system
- Consider Privacy Awareness training for staff handling and collecting data
- Automate privacy controls where possible

GET TO KNOW AND APPLY:

- [USAID's Policy on Development Data Development](#) and relevant US law National legal frameworks for data handling and privacy protection (in [Niger](#) and [Burkina Faso](#))
- [USAID policy and procedure guidance on data responsibility](#)
- Automated Directives System (ADS) contains the organization and functions of USAID, along with the policies and procedures that guide the Agency's programs and operations including expected data protections
- Partners' data policy and procedure
- International standards, norms and practices such as [ISO 27701](#)
- USAID guidelines detailed in [Section 889](#) for communications equipment procurement

SUGGESTED ACTIONS TO ENSURE DATA RESPONSIBILITY

DWG members proposed best practices for securing data and technologies practiced within their various projects during May 2022 workshops. These include:

ACTIONS TO MAKE DATA SAFER¹:

- Assess needs and train employees on data privacy
- Store data on removable media away from the workplace
- Identify and limit the people in charge of data management
- Do not share data via email
- Provide secure cloud spaces for data storage but avoid free services, as they are less secure
- Do not share personal data
- Limit access to sensitive data
- Lock down devices containing sensitive data
- Avoid storing data on multiple media
- Codify the folders containing sensitive information
- Secure access to data (connection parameters)
- Make data managers aware of the security of personal data
- Manage devices containing sensitive data (limit access to certain sites to prevent intrusions into internal systems)
- Add passwords to access data; change passwords regularly
- Opt for cloud hosting with credible providers
- Keep data collection applications updated to benefit from the latest security features
- Implement a geolocation system for lost/stolen devices
- Save sensitive data outside of physical premises
- Put in place technologies (adapted devices) against climatic hazards (lightning, electrical problems, etc.)
- Secure the devices containing data with passwords
- Connect only to sites that respect data security protocols (https)
- Back up data on external removable media
- Do not share data via social networks

ACTIONS TO STRENGTHEN SUSTAINABILITY OF DATA PROTECTION EFFORTS:

- Establish a mechanism to validate the reliability of data and encourage the sharing of appropriately anonymized raw data within and between USAID projects.
- Study the feasibility of ANPTIC in Burkina and ANSI in Niger being the national data repository so that data is not lost after a project closes, data sharing is facilitated between projects of different donors.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The DWG meetings resulted in a set of five practice-oriented recommendations on how to ensure data responsibility within USAID funded activities:

FOCUS ON SECURING DATA: Data security is part of a risk control environment and therefore needs to align with the partner organizations' procedures and protocols. The procedures should

¹ Assessment to be potentially developed into organization-specific Standard Operating Procedures.

include handling of paper and electronic records, ensure policy and protocols for data sharing are in place and all relevant personnel are trained.

PROTECT DATA PRIVACY: Disaggregated data linked to an individual or place are at greatest privacy and security risk. PII can be used to recognize an individual or trace their actions and movements. Restricting access, reducing collection and storage, and proper disposal of PII is essential to data risk management. Removing PII and aggregating data are steps that should be taken when sharing data. All data managers should create a data checklist to ensure data privacy.

SET UP DATA RESPONSIBILITY PROCEDURES AND TRAIN ON THEM: To use and exchange information, key risks must be adequately managed. Privacy risk management procedures ensure data elements are being shared in line with regulatory requirements, especially when handling information about individuals. Data security risks are minimized with appropriate governance and procedures about information platforms, processing, access, classification, and monitoring.

PRACTICE DATA MINIMIZATION: Data minimization is a strategy that ensures that any data processing is fit for the defined purpose. Collecting no more data than what is absolutely necessary is the best strategy for ensuring privacy protection and data security. Data minimization is not merely a choice but is enshrined in national and international law that carry significant penalties for organizations and individuals that process data or initiate international transfers of data. Simply, only collect data that will be used for important and well-defined purposes.

UNDERTAKE PRIVACY IMPACT ASSESSMENTS REGULARLY: A Privacy Impact Assessment (PIA) assists organizations in identifying and managing data privacy risks associated with any new activity, such as new programs, technology, or policies. For more details on when a PIA is needed, and general PIA questions, please see [PIA Guidance](#).

FOR FURTHER READING

- [USAID Digital strategy](#)
- [USAID program cycle guidance](#)
- [ADS 508, Privacy Program](#)
- [ADS 545 - Information Systems security](#)
- [ADS Chapter 579 - USAID Development Data](#)
- [Data responsibility FHI 360](#)
- [USAID – activity location data](#)

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